

**EFFECTIVENESS OF MULTIMEDIA E- BOOK INSTRUCTIONAL SYSTEM FOR
TEACHING GEOGRAPHICAL CONCEPT AT SECONDARY LEVEL
STUDENTS**

Dr. Vilas Bhanudas. Bandgar

Assistant Professor,

Uma Shikshanshastra Mahavidyalaya B.Ed. Pandharpur, Solapur. Maharashtra.

India...vilasbandgar@gmail.com

Abstract: Education is ongoing process throughout the life. In 21st century the world is rapidly growing and changing; to cope up with this modern education system is also changing rapidly. Together with changes new expectation appeared towards teacher from the society as a part of which teacher's role is also changing as per. All the developed and developing nations are focusing on the improvement, generation and sharing of the knowledge and also the flow of the new technology along with our country. In the national and international policy debates the proper knowledge occupies the central stage, in the age of productivity and innovation. Education fields include teaching – learning, research and management. For good teaching- learning practice, it should be interactive which need large amount of information. Computer is in the best storage for such huge information which can easily get used for different purpose. Using Multimedia Instructional System in classroom at school is a new paradigm especially in developing countries. Multimedia Instructional System offers students, teacher and school an additional medium or tool of instruction that enhance learning process. And so the present research work can provide useful to the field of education as well as for nation too. In the changing world as education system is changing, it needs new things to be get integrated in the education teaching learning process. So, Multimedia Instructional System containing multimedia is used for the teaching purpose at every stage of education system along with secondary level.

Key words: Education, innovation, Multimedia E-Book Instructional System, etc.

1.1 Introduction:

In the rapidly changing world, the concept of education system is also changing which ultimately needed the changed and more powerful role of teachers. Teacher is important part of the

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educational systems in which role of the teacher is not only having subject related knowledge but teacher should Perform the multitasking role like mentor, tutor, Guide, philosopher provider and also role model for students. The modern age regarded as a time in which information has become a valuable thing that is quickly and disseminate and easily available especially through the use of computer technology which is used worldwide. Exploration of new technology advancement in present machinery or technology is the specialty of this age. Also, computerization is the major factor. Education fields include teaching – learning process, research and management. For good teaching – learning practice, it should be interactive which need large amount of information. Computer is the best storage for such huge information which can easily get used for different purpose. Also for the good interaction and effective teaching, good quality of communication is needed. This is new and distinct period of time, in which technology affects all activities of our lives, especially the younger generation who were born post- internet, the education system is in the revetment of confront to adopt to the technological developments of the 21st century. (Hamedi& Ezleila,2015) Today’s educational system must provide lifelong learners who are able to process large amount knowledge every day. The traditional educational system is teacher centered. In this system students receive knowledge only transmitted by the teacher and somewhat from book which is out dated now.

Thus, the good students are those who have good listening skills, take note summarizing contents and passed in the test. On the other hand in the students need to be independent and lead themselves, react ver. actively to solve the problem, and acts as generator of knowledge in the 21st century that should be adjusted to the student’s own learning goals. (Hamedi& Ezleila,2015)

1.2. Conceptual and Operational Definitions of the Terms:

1. Effectiveness:

Effectiveness also defines as, “The degree to which something is successful in producing a desired result, success. The proposed paper aims to take effectiveness means total score scored by sample Std IX students from Progress Vidyalaya, Tal- Pandharpur school for the experimental purpose after experiment.

2. Multimedia E- Book Instructional System:

In this paper Multimedia E- Book Instructional System means Instructional System containing multimedia via the integration of multiple forms of media. Multimedia assigns to computerized information that is presented contemporaneously in more than one medium. It consists not necessarily all but sometimes few elements, of the following elements: text; still graphic images, motion graphics, animations, hyper media, photographs, video and audio i.e. sound, music and narration and so on many more for teaching Geography subject of Std IX

3. Secondary level students:

A secondary school is also known as High School. It usually provides educational instruction for students during the period from ages 14 to 16 i.e., here students consider from the Std. IX of Progress Vidyalaya, Tal- Pandharpur school.

1.3. Objectives of The Research:

1. To study the effectiveness of Multimedia E-book Instructional System in teaching Geography subject at secondary level.
2. To compare the effectiveness of conventional method of teaching and Multimedia E-Book Instructional System method for teaching Geography.

1.4. Research Methodology:

The main purpose of the present study was to observe effectiveness of Multimedia E-Book Instructional System for secondary level students and to see its effectiveness on the performance of the students. Multimedia technique was used to develop the instructional system. The following paragraphs show the effectiveness of Multimedia e-book Instructional System for teaching geography of present research. The investigator planned goals and objectives of Multimedia Instructional System of teaching concept in Geography and designed proposed system for Std. IX students of Progress Vidyalaya, Tal- Pandharpur. The internal evaluation of a Multimedia Instructional System of teaching concept in Geography done within the subject expert. The investigator analyzed and interpreted the data obtained in internal evaluation. A per -test of 20 marks administrated on the sample. The answer-scripts were assessed; the scores were collected,

analyzed and interpreted. The experimental group instructed by using Multimedia Instructional System of teaching concept in Geography while control group was instructed by using Conventional Instructional System. A post-test of 20 marks administered on the sample. The responses of the students were collected in terms of scores. The data was analyzed and interpreted. 'Is the Multimedia Instructional System used in experimental group of students proved helpful to the students from the group?' was question to be answered. A comparative analysis and interpretation of the gains in achievement was done to answer the question. Conclusions were drawn about the effectiveness of the Multimedia Instructional System of teaching concept in geography and suggestions were stated.

1.5. Analysis & Interpretation of Data:

The data was analyzed with the help of statistical and non-statistical measures. The technique of test was used. The investigators tabulated the collected data and calculated the t- values to compare achievement of students from control and experimental group.

1.6. Conclusions:

1. Teaching of Geography subject at secondary level in school with the help of Multimedia Instructional E- Book System is more effective and better then teaching through conventional teaching method.
2. The academic achievement performed by students are more through Multimedia Instructional E- Book System and got better result in every subject then the students taught through conventional teaching method.

These findings of the study completely indicated that the Multimedia Instructional E- Book System help to the student for more academic achievement, more will to study, better environment for learning process.

3. As we have already stated that the effect of conventional method is cannot denied, but a Combination of skills and experience of teacher and the use of multimedia E- Book teaching Instruction will definitely bring about a more effective teaching and learning

1.7. Recommendations:

1. It is recommended that self learning material be developed for every secondary level teacher while teaching the subject like Geography.
2. Multimedia E- Book Instructional System is necessity of the teachers for secondary level to show more effect for teaching and learning process in the subject Geography.
3. The teacher should have proper understanding of the subject which they studied and without proper understanding of the subject; one cannot use multimedia technology approach.
4. The teacher should comprehend the concept of implementation of multimedia E- book Instructional System for Geography subject at secondary level of educational system.

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